

Bis(ethylenediamine)copper(II)benzoylacetone Dihydrate

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As a part of the general programme on the studies of the linkage modes of β -diketones, in transition metal complexes uni- and bis- C^3 -bonded β -diketonato, C^1 -bonded bridging β -diketonato, outer-sphere β -diketonate, central carbon bonded hetero- β -diketonato and mixed β -diketonato complexes have been reported¹. Reaction of bis (benzoylacetone) copper(II) with ethylenediamine was studied in dichloromethane and dichloromethane-water mixture resulting in the isolation of $[Cu(bzac)_2en]$ and $[Cu(bzac)_2en_2] \cdot 2H_2O$.

Results and Discussion

The light green crystalline complex (Table 1) has the composition $[Cu(bzac)_2en]$. It is soluble in common organic solvents and the acetone solution of the complex has low molar conductance value indicating its non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment measurement indicates the presence of one unpaired electron. Infrared spectra shows the presence of chelated benzoylacetone and coordinated ethylene diamine. The band $\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=C}$ was observed at 1 600, 1 565, 1 510, $\nu_{O=C-O}$ at 460 and ν_{Cu-N} at 380 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectra in chloroform solution exhibited one broad band at 15.4 kK (ϵ 45) suggesting a six-coordinated octahedral configuration for the compound.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ΛM		μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
	($m \Omega^{-1} cm^2$)			C	H	N
$[Cu(bzac)_2en]$	144	10.5	1.80	58.85	5.54	5.92
$[Cu(bzac)_2en_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	247	17.5	1.81	52.75	7.02	10.45
				(53.00)	(7.35)	(10.30)

On the otherhand, the blue crystalline compound $[Cu(bzac)_2(en)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ is insoluble in non-polar organic solvents but soluble in water. Magnetic moment value suggests the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for Cu^{II} ion. Infrared spectra showed $\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=C}$ band at a higher frequency region (1 610, 1 575, 1 520 cm^{-1}) compared to the green compound. There is no band due to ν_{Cu-O} around 460 cm^{-1} , but ν_{Cu-N} band was found around 385 cm^{-1} . A broad band appeared around 3 500 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} indicating the presence of lattice water. In the visible region, for

the complex $[Cu(bzac)_2en_2] \cdot 2H_2O$, a band was observed at 18.6 kK suggesting that the compound has possibly a four-coordinated planar structure and there is a very weak interaction of the oxygen atoms of benzoylacetone molecule with the metal ion in the axial position.

It is inferred that the β -diketone moiety is quite labile as has been observed in case of many other transition metal β -diketonates.

Experimental

Bis(benzoylacetone)copper(II) was stirred magnetically with equimolar proportion of ethylenediamine in dichloromethane (10 ml) at room temperature for 0.5 h. Volume of the solution was then reduced to 5 ml and kept in the refrigerator when light green crystals separated out.

Bis(benzoylacetone)copper(II) was stirred with excess ethylenediamine in dichloromethane containing water for 2 h at room temperature. Volume of the solution was then reduced and the solution was kept in a refrigerator overnight. Blue crystalline compounds that separated out were dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Composition of the complexes was determined by elemental analysis. Molar conductance was measured in acetone medium ($10^{-3} M$) using a Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 and 337 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra (in 0.01 M $CHCl_3$) on a Hilger-Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer.

References

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